

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 4

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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Elektron nashr. 882 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Organizational Behavior and Leadership.....	10
Ibrokhim Gulomov	
Baliqchilikda klasterlarini tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari	18
Olim Murtazayev, Muydinov Olim Bekmurotovich	
Оценка состояния привлечения инвестиций в сферу туризма Узбекистана и механизмы управления	24
Арзиматов Бобирмирзо Зокирджон угли	
Biologik aktivlar buxgalteriya hisobni milliy va xalqaro standartlarga muvofiq takomillashtirish masalalari ...	27
Axmadaliyeva Zebo Abduxalimovna	
Aholi yashash joylarida yong'in risklarini bartaraf etish xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari	32
Aziz Zikriyoev	
O'zbekistonda ilmiy darajali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimi boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasi va vazifalari.....	40
Beknaeva Shaxnoza Vladimirovna	
Mintaqaviy turizmning iqtisodiyot rivojlanishiga ta'siri (O'zbekiston turistik xizmatlar bozori misolida).....	45
D. B. O'roqova	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ko'paytirishning asosiy yo'llari.....	50
Ibrohimov Boburmirro Baxtiyor o'g'li, Sayfiddinov Sarvarbek Anvarbek o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarining aksiyalar bozorida faoliyati tahlili: muammolar va yechimlar	55
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
Qurilishda modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish asosida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini oshirish	63
Islamov Ozodjon	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion salohiyatini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	67
J. K. Boymurodov	
Mamlakatda yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	72
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
BlokchEYn texnologiyalari yordamida raqamli iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish	77
Karabayev Rustam Zafarovich, Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida zamonaviy mehnat bozorining rivojlanishi	84
Layli Mirzayeva	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda investitsion resurslardan samarali foydalanish mexanizmlari.....	88
Luiza Komilovna Xaydarova	
Umumta'lim muassasalari sonining ekonometrik tahlilini pedagogik metodlar yordamida amalga oshirish....	93
Ravshanova Muhayyo Maxmanazarovna	
O'zbekiston tarixiy shaharlarida turistik faoliyati shakllanishi va ularni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	98
Meliqulov G'ayrat Abdug'afforovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish va ilmiy tadqiqot rivojlanishining havo ifloslanish darajasiga ta'siri	105
Murodullayev Kamoliddin Sherzod o'g'li, Sadibekova Bibisora Djapparovna, Turdiqulov Farrux Ravshanjon o'g'li	
Hududlarni rivojlantirish va "yashil iqtisodiyot"ni shakllantirishning ekologik muammolari.....	110
Maxkamov Saidafzal Saidkamol o'g'li, Yigitaliyeva Dilnavo Mansurjon qizi	
Ekoturizm obyektining tasniflanishi va alohida xususiyatlari	116
Qodirov Azizjon Anvarovich	
Mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimida sifat menejmentidan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	121
Saidqulova Furuza Farmonovna	
Bo'lajak iqtisodchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalari.....	125
Shukurova Marifat Xodjiakbar qizi	
Ta'limning bosqichlari va ularning inson kapitalini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati	129
To'rayeva Hurriyat To'yqulovna	

Hududlarda to'g'ridan to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish dasturini amalga oshirishda marketingni rivojlantirish yo'llari	136
Xamidov O. X., Tojiyeva A. F.	
Investitsiyalar marketingining strategik aspektlari.....	143
Xodjamberdiyeva Dilnoza Bahtiyorovna	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda investitsion muhit jozibadorligini oshirishga nazariy qarashlar	149
A. Bektemirov, A. A. Abdurahmonov	
Qishloq xo'jaligi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	154
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Ochilov Narzullo Fayzulloyevich	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari.....	159
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Turizm sohasi uchun yuqori malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashda davlat va xususiy sherikchilikning o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlili.....	165
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich	
Mamlakatimizda turizm tashkilotlari faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida marketing instrumentlari orqali samarali tizim yaratish.....	169
Suyunova Kamilla Baxromovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida agrokimyo xizmatlar ko'rsatishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	173
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishni faollashtirish muammolari.....	178
Xomitov K. Z., Masharipova S. R.	
Considerations on the Problem of Illegal Migration and Human Trafficking	183
Azamatova Gulmira Bayirbekovna, Otarbayeva Guljan Kobeyevna	
Sustainable Development and Environmental Economics in Uzbekistan: A Focus on Carbon Pricing and Renewable Energy	186
Muhammadiyev Po'latjon Ilhomjon o'g'li, Urganbayeva Dilnoza Toxtasinovna	
The use of Digital Technologies in the Provision Of Utilities to the Population	192
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich, Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna, Alijonov Jamshid Alijon o'g'li	
The Current State of the Digital Economy in the Agrarian Sphere: Problems and Solutions	196
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Behavioral Theory of the Firm.....	201
Egamberdieva Oydin Abror qizi	
The Role of Information Technologies in Increasing the Capitalization of Commercial Banks	207
Egamova Makhfurat Esanovna	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	211
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Совершенствование методологии экспертизы инвестиционных проектов	216
Бекимбетова Гулнора Маратовна	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	223
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Меры по снижению доли теневой экономики в стране.....	228
Махмудова Юлдузхон Бахромжон кизи, Сафаров Гиёсиддин Абдуллаевич ўгли	
Формирование национальной инновационной системы – одна из приоритетных задач повышения конкурентоспособности Республики Узбекистан	232
Н. М. Махмудов, А. А. Алиев, З. А. Мирзоев	
Мониторинг и анализ современного состояния и развития промышленности в Узбекистане.....	237
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Исмоилова Малика Дилшодовна	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов.....	243
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	
Роль применения ключевых показателей эффективности труда на предприятиях.....	249
Рахматуллаева Шахноза Хамидовна	

Влияние цифровой трансформации на инвестиционную привлекательность Узбекистана.....	255
Саиткамоллов Муҳаммадхожа Сабирходжа угли, Маркабаева Жансая Айбек кызы	
Организация и координация методической помощи при управлении педагогическими кадрами	261
Хакимова Майя Юрьевна	
Интеграция узбекистана в мировое экономическое содружество путем унификации бухгалтерского учета на основе МСФО	266
Зарипова Саёхат Зафаровна	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	271
Abduqodirova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan jismoniy shaxslarga ajratilgan kreditlarning joriy tahlili.....	276
Abdusalomov Jaxongir O'ktam o'g'li	
Globalashuv sharoitida mamlakatimizda sug'urta bozorini raqamlashtirishning ahamiyati	282
Anvarova Z.	
The Role of Parents and Teachers in Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle in Children.....	286
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
A Study of the Importance of Green Economy in Uzbekistan Sustainable Economic Development and its Measurement Indicators in Relation to Environment.....	291
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltayevna, Tairova Zarnigor Mammot qizi	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	296
Avazov Iloxom Ravshanovich	
Foydani soliqqa tortish obyekti sifatidagi iqtisodiy tarkibi.....	301
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida aholining uy-joy bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini tahlili.....	309
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich	
Review of Methodological Approaches to Enterprises Financial Condition Analysis.....	314
Ismailova Maxbuba Mirxalilovna	
Innovatsion rivojlanish sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini tasniflanishining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	319
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
Korxonalarda benchmarking strategiyalarini qo'llashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	325
Narziyeva Dilafiruz Muxtorovna	
Davlat budjetining soliqsiz daromadlari shakllanishini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	330
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Mamlakatimizda sanoat ishlab chiqarishi korxonalarining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	334
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
Moliyaviy natijalar to'g'risidagi hisobotni moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlar talablari asosida tuzish.....	339
Pardayeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida qo'shma korxonasi faoliyatining tahlili.....	343
Rashidov Jamshid Xamidovich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishida oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni.....	348
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich, Saloxiddinov Zuxriddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatishning ilmiy asoslari.....	352
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida telekommunikatsiya sohasini rivojlantirish ilmiy asoslari.....	356
Toshmatov Salohiddin Zayniddinovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarni joriy etishning huquqiy masalalari.....	360
Turg'unov Saloxiddin Jamol o'g'li, Mirzayeva Mohidil Vohidovna	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda korxonalarining moliyaviy baqarorligini yaxshilash masalalari	366
Usmanova Guljahon Ulug'bek qizi	
Franshizalarni jalb qilishda davlat boshqaruvi tizimida marketing tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati	371
Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	

Transport Decarbonization Strategy.....	377
Yarashova Vasila Kamalovna, Muradov Bekzod Xidirnazar ugli	
Temir yo'l transportida ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	382
Yermatova Dilnoza Axmadjonovna	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	387
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlarini ko'rsatish samaradorligi va sifatini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tizimi.....	390
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlari sifatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularni baholash	394
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulkiga soliq solishni takomillashtirish.....	399
Abdullayev Zafarjon Alijonovich, Zaydullayev Abduhabib Boliqul o'g'li	
Sug'urta tashkilotlarida hisob siyosatini ishlab chiqishning ahamiyati.....	404
Abduraimova Maftunaxon Axmatovna	
Bank risklarini boshqarishning xalqaro tajribalari.....	409
Abdurasulov Jaxongir Abduvaliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari ijtimoiy ma'sulligini ta'minlash mexanizmining amal qilish darajasi.....	416
Bayisbayev Javlon Nurlanovich	
Qishloq aholisining qishloq xo'jaligida bilim va innovatsiyalarni o'zlashtirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni iqtisodiy baholash (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	421
Bozorova Lobar Nuralevna	
Направления совершенствования инновационных стратегий в деятельности промышленных предприятий.....	427
Дониерова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
Mol-mulk solig'ining korxonalar faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	432
Qudiyarov Kishibay Ramatullayevich	
Banklar reytingini aniqlash va barqarorligini ta'minlashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	438
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida tijorat banklarining aktiv va passiv operatsiyalarini innovatsion usullar orqali boshqarishni takomillashtirish	442
Mo'minova Ma'suda Baxtiyarovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini dasturiy ta'minot asosida tashkil etish: muammo va yechimlar.....	447
Nazarova Kamola Sattoral qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan tartibga solish konsepsiyasi.....	453
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ahamiyati hamda uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	460
Nurullayeva Shaxnoza, Saydullayeva Saodat	
Tijorat banklari inson kapitali samaradorligini baholashda KPI ko'rsatkichlaridan foydalanish mexanizmlari	467
Turaeva Mastura Kurbanovna	
Сущность и особенности инвестиционно-строительного процесса	471
А. Бектемиров, Б.М.Абдувалиев	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni boshqarishning dolzarb masalalari.....	478
Saidov Hayotjon Raxmatulloevich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	482
Sa'dullayeva Asalxon Muzaffarovna	
Ko'p tarmoqli fermer xo'jaliklarining raqobatbardoshlikni baholash usullari	485
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Teshayev Mirolim Djumayevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida soliq yukini optimallashtirish mexanizmi	490
To'xsanov Quدراتило Nozimovich	

Davlat sektorida ichki audit tadbirlarini umumiy rejalashtirish	495
Xamidova Z. U.	
Aholi moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish va uning ahamiyati.....	501
Xudayarova Xurshida Abdunazarovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	505
Xudoyberdiyev Jamshid Juraboy o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida buxgalteriya hisobi va ichki auditni takomillashtirish	511
Shaymatova Nargiza Ashurovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sug'urta xizmatlari.....	516
Shodmonova Odina G'ofur qizi	
Fuqarolar davlat pensiya ta'minoti tizimining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	520
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
Aholiga bank xizmatlari ko'rsatishning ijtimoiy ahamiyati.....	525
Eldor Uskanov	
Innovatsion boshqaruvning ilg'or xorijiy tajribalari	530
Yusupova Jamila Karamatdinovna	
Neft-gaz korxonalarini moliyaviy-iqtisodiy faoliyati natijalari tahlili ("O'ZBEKNEFTGAZ" AJ misolida)	534
Umurzoqov Jamoliddin Sherbekovich	
Korxonalarda savdo marketing faoliyati samaradorligini baholash.....	541
Sobirov Azizbek Avzbekovich	
Moliyaviy firibgarliklarga qarshi kurashishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	548
Gadaev Ismat Yadgarovich	
Hududlarda islom iqtisodiyoti tamoyillari asosida amalga oshirilgan investitsion loyihalar: to'siqlar va yechimlar	551
Irgasheva Gulbahor Sodiqovna	
O'zbekistonda investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanish asosida oziq-ovqat sanoati samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	554
Kobilova Nasiba Xurramovna	
Foreign Economic Relations as a Factor of Effective Functioning of the Economy	561
Bakhodurova Sulkhya Azizkhodjaevna, Li Marina Rudolfovna, Mukhtarova Donata Ravshanbekovna, Romashkin Roman Anatolyevich	
Modern Approaches to the Organization and Development of the Consumer Services Market.....	566
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Ishlab chiqarish siklini qisqartirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	570
Odina Nabiyevna Tuychiyeva, Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
Asalarichilik mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish.....	575
Rashidova Xadicha Tursunalievna	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida bank faoliyatini iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish yo'llari	581
Raxmanov Mexridin Sindarovich	
Korporativ boshqaruv amaliyoti bo'yicha hisobot tuzish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	586
Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	592
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiyotda turizm o'rnini statistik baholash uslubiyoti.....	595
Zilola Jumanova	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	602
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Блокчейн-технология и информационная безопасность в цифровой экономике Узбекистана.....	607
Кадиров Алишер Исмаилович	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов	611
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	

O'zbekistonda zamonaviy kabel va sim mahsulotlari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyatiga nazar.....	617
Rashidova Odina Olimjon qizi	
Современные тенденции развития валютных отношений в Узбекистане	622
Камалов Камолалдин Кахрамонович	
Sug'urta sohasining O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni	626
Sharobiddinov Akramjon Goyibbayevich	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi va undan O'zbekistonda foydalanish yo'nalishlari	630
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
Modeling the Stackelberg strategy in a linear model (linear city) Hotteling.....	635
Musayeva Shaira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
Mulkning kapitallashuvi darajasini iqtisodiy jihatdan amalga oshirish samaradorligini baholash uslublari.....	644
Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini amaliy holati va ekonometrik tahlillari: ATB "Aloqabank" misolida.....	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyeвна	
O'zbekistonda "yashil iqtisodiyot" muhitida kreditlash va moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari	654
Taxir Urkinbayev	
Budjet tashkilotlarida ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilishning xususiyatlari.....	658
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
Chinese Commercial Banks Experience in Asset Diversification	663
Uktamova Nozima Narzulla kizi	
Sanoat taraqqiyotida ishlab chiqarish korxonalarini ustuvor rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	667
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich	
Анализ деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана по кредитованию физических лиц.....	673
Базарова Нигора Равшановна	
Mahalliy va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning innovatsion jarayonlarga ta'sirini baholash.....	684
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	689
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Xusanov Faxriddin Jamoliddin o'g'li	
Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi.....	694
O. N. Djurayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda sanoat tarmog'ining davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishini baholash	699
Otaboyeva Dildora	
Nobank kredit tashkilotlarining moliyaviy xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	705
Raimov Xurshid Muxtorovich	
Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy injiniringni qo'llash istiqbollari	711
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi moliya bozorida tijorat banklari faoliyati: muammo va yechimlar	716
Toymuxamedov Ibroxim Rixsiboevich, Jumaev Islombek Akram o'g'li	
Agrar ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	723
Boltayev Nurali Shiramatovich, Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich, Abdiyev Izzat Risqiboyevich	
O'zini o'zi band qilgan shaxslardan olinadigan soliqlarni takomillashtirish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jilovlash masalalari	731
Davranov Iskandar Jumayevich	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarni tartibga solish va nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	738
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Role of Private and Public Kindergartens in Early Childhood Development	744
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
"Yashil" enegriya quvvatlarini barpo etish iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash asosi sifatida.....	749
Muminova Elnoraxon Abdukarimovna, Umarova Dilnoza Oybek qizi	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda CVP-tahlilni tashkil etishning muammoli jihatlari	754
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardayevich	

Korxonada likvidlik riskini minimallashtirish orqali uning moliyaviy barqarorligini saqlab qolish	759
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Развитие международных торгово-экономических связей Республики Узбекистан	766
Ким Татьяна Валерьевна, Гофуржонова Шахрибону Бахромжон кизи	
Kapital qurilishni boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning dolzarb masalalari	774
A. Bektemirov, M. U. Sarimsoqov	
O'zbekiston mehnat bozorida yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish.....	780
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdiyevich, Bahromov Shahzod Fazliddinovich	
Роль имиджа в улучшении инвестиционной привлекательности высших учебных заведений.....	787
Жанзаков Бекзот, Жонузоков Мирзабек	
Innovatsion kichik tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha xorij tajribasi va uni mamlakat iqtisodiyotida qo'llash imkoniyati.....	795
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Eshqulova Dilorom Abduravupovna	
Перспективы развития банковского сектора в Узбекистане для иностранных туристов	802
Муминов Шахзод Низомиддинович, Каримова Азиза Махомадризоевна	
Innovatsion faoliyat moliyaviy modellari va mexanizmlarini rivojlantirishning konseptual asoslari	806
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmoqlarini innovatsion rivojlantirish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda samarali foydalanish yo'llari	814
Ishniyazov Baxrom Normamatovich	
Turistik xizmatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va marketing tadqiqotlari.....	819
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna	
Qoraqalpog'iston qishloq xo'jaligi: asosiy muammolar va rivojlanishining ustuvor yo'nalishlari	823
Yeshimbetov Uktamjon Xudaybergenovich	
Iqtisodiyotning erkinlashtirilishi sharoitlarida kichik biznes sektori rivojlanishining imkoniyatlari.....	832
Botirova R. A., Sirojiddinov I. Q.	
Kriptoalyuta va blokcheyn tadqiqotlari: tendensiyalar va istiqbollar	835
Berdiqulov Jurabek	
Bank risklarni monitoring qilish tizimini takomillashtirish	837
Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	
O'zbekiston hududlariga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda ko'p qavatli "yashil" fermer xo'jaliklarini tashkil etishning ahamiyati	843
Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatining mahalliy budjet daromadlarini oshirish yo'llari va uni arima modeli asosida prognozlash.....	846
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ining mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va undagi tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash.....	856
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati	863
Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	
Turizm bozorini rivojlantirishda mehnat bozorining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati	872
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna, Berdikulov Jurabek	
Проблемы расчета определения и планирования прибыли предприятий в условиях модернизации экономики	876
Алиева С.С.	

THE CURRENT STATE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE AGRARIAN SPHERE: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: This article describes the existing problems of the system of digitalization of the agrarian sphere in the digital economy. In the agrarian sphere, methods based on the scientific support of the digital economy have been developed. The introduction of digital technologies into sphere dramatically increases labor productivity and reduces risks to agriculture.

Key words: agrarian sphere, digital economy, digital technology, scientific research, economic technologies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyotda agrar sohani raqamlashtirish tizimining mavjud muammolari tasvirlangan. Agrar sohada raqamli iqtisodiyotni ilmiy qo'llab-quvvatlashga asoslangan usullar ishlab chiqilgan. Sohaga raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish mehnat unumdorligini keskin oshiradi va qishloq xo'jaligi uchun xavflarni kamaytiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: agrar soha, raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli texnologiya, ilmiy tadqiqotlar, iqtisodiy texnologiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны существующие проблемы системы оцифровки аграрного сфера в цифровой экономике. В аграрной сфере разработаны методы, основанные на научном обеспечении цифровой экономики. Внедрение цифровых технологий в отрасль резко повысит производительность труда и снизит риски для сельского хозяйства.

Ключевые слова: аграрный сфера, цифровая экономика, цифровые технологии, научные исследования, экономические технологии.

INTRODUCTION

The country's high pace of development of Science and technology-technologies in the agrarian sphere and the development of productive forces provide an opportunity to create traditional technologies. Today it is an important driving force of the economy as a source of information resources, services, goods, value added and employment. In the fund for the penetration and development of Information Processes in the economic sphere, such forms of economic activity as internet stores, Internet banks, payment systems begin to develop gradually, new types of banknotes began to appear, a whole branch of the economy-the digital economy-is being built.

In the agrarian sphere, the extended approach determines that the digital economy is economic production using digital technologies. That is, the digital economy is an economic activity built on the basis of e-commerce, as well as electronic money exchange. Usually, these conditions mean the operation of electronic services aimed at the sale of electronic goods and services, often there is a process of exchanging electronic money between participants in electronic transactions. The effective implementation of the digital economy has a significant impact on the socio-economic development of the country, Society serves to master new aspects of development.

Agriculture is a field based on agrarian science. Almost all elements are subject to digital technology. It includes a large collection of data created and collected by agricultural producers using digital technologies, as well as the entire cycle of the product; calculation with land for the production of food products, adaptation of consumer characteristics to the supply of food to consumers.

To reconcile the bottom-up and top-down definitions of the Digital Economy, Bukht and Heeks stated that the Digital Economy consists of all sectors making extensive use of digital technologies, as opposed to sectors making intensive use of digital technologies ^[1].

Due to significant changes in the economy, the country's interest in the digital economy has grown significantly. Modern technologies and platforms have helped to reduce costs for enterprises and individuals, as well as provide quick and easy interaction, at the expense of minimizing personal communication with customers, partners and government organizations. The result was a digital or electronic economy based on network resources.

The effectiveness of the digital economy is influenced not only by the presence of Information Technology coverage and infrastructure, but also by standard economic criteria such as the business environment, human capital and successful management tools. Consequently, economic development relies on them, that is, these criteria play an important role in the development of the digital economy, as before.

Although there is a trend of relative growth in agricultural production, but measures for the full and efficient use of existing resources and production facilities have not yet been sufficiently organized and implemented [1].

For the progress of the digital economy, developed and developing countries, agriculture in particular is one of the priorities.

RESEARCH METHOD IN THE AGRARIAN SPHERE

At the present stage of development of the economy of Uzbekistan, information technology actively penetrates into all branches of Agriculture. It simplifies the life of the population of the country, increases labor productivity and speeds up information and communication processes. As a separate field of scientific knowledge, the digital economy has a certain methodological basis.

Gulyamov noted that "the digital economy consists of a chain of interrelated production and management processes, an integral element of which is the exchange of information that is carried out using chainoo digital technologies" [3]:

Methodological foundations of information type economics.

The economy of the information type, like any field of scientific knowledge, is based on the use of two main methodological groups: general methods; private methods.

General methods are used at all levels of knowledge.

As for private methods, they are used directly in the economy.

The economy studies the interaction of economic entities that occurs in the process of creating, distributing and using goods, including information. The nature of such interactions directly depends on the level of Social Development.

Research methods play a special big role. Scientific research of economic processes in the agrarian sphere requires the creation of information collection, transmission and processing functions in order to meet the information needs of researchers. Currently, the market of software products has a wide range of automated workplaces for various specialists of the agrarian sphere, which should ensure the high efficiency of economic activity of enterprises.

Varnavsky believes that the development of research in the field of institutional theory, in which such categories as information and transactions are balanced, will help overcome scientific difficulties [4].

Therefore, we can see the application of research methods in the digital economy of the agrarian sphere (Table 1).

RESULTS OF DIGITIZATION IN AGRICULTURE

The complexity of digital transformation processes requires the formation of a special mechanism for its initiation and management. It is proposed to understand the mechanism of digital transformation of agricultural producers as the scale of planned digitization, priority of directions and the speed of transformational processes, a set of structural and functional elements that allow them to start and control the digitization processes of economic entities within the framework of the implementation of digital development strategies.

The mechanism of digital transformation is mainly aimed at eliminating barriers to the digital development of agricultural producers.

This mechanism should allow agricultural producers to focus on different strategies and models of digitization due to the significant differentiation of production and management processes in terms of the level of informatization, financial provision of digital transformational processes, each of these models should meet the goals of digital development in a complex way. At the same time, the mechanism of digital transformation should take into account a very high change in production technologies and means of their implementation, fundamental changes in the composition and quality of resources necessary for agricultural production, as well as the need to modernize the system of inter-object relations formed within stable value chains.

Table 1: Methods of research in the digital economy of the agrarian sphere¹

Sphere	Research methods
Agrarian sphere	- In the agrarian sphere, it is necessary to create scientific developments that ensure the effectiveness of the research work of the scientific institution. Automation of research work, the use of economic and mathematical methods, the use of databases, access to Internet resources are important factors in conducting the work of researchers, as a result of which not only opportunities, but also the ability to quickly and efficiently carry out their tasks. The modern development of the sphere is associated with the use of knowledge-based factors in management activities: organizational, production-economic, strategic plans, technical-technological, socio-labor, regulatory and legal, information. These can be seen in the example of the use of the latest technologies in agriculture and animal husbandry, new technical means, improvement of the agricultural system. The introduction of scientific and technical developments and innovations into practice is a source of economic growth, which serves to increase labor productivity, significantly reduce the cost of product production and increase the volume of production..
	- monitoring must be carried out to assess the innovation potential of agricultural producers, which involves questioning certain groups of respondents. The experience of sending surveys for the application of innovations in enterprises by email does not give the desired result, since the percentage of their replenishment is very low. For monitoring in research institutes, funds are not allocated from the budgetary side, since it is necessary to provide scientific personnel with funds for travel expenses. The issue of creating a single information field of Agriculture and, accordingly, the problems of Agrarian science, as well as commodity producers do not have enough funds to purchase agricultural innovation technologies, techniques.
	- agricultural sectors have great risks, since the network is closely related to natural-climatic conditions. In agriculture, farmers and peasant farms are engaged in seasonal work throughout their activities, since, high yields in the country lead to a decrease in prices, as well as the demand for agricultural products has uncertainties in terms of price and income. The result is a situation where, instead of the high profits calculated by the producers, they receive much less profits or suffer losses. The peculiarity of Agriculture is that not only demand, but also supply becomes flexible. Here, the reasons for the flexibility of the offer in terms of prices and income, the fact that the land supply is not in the same standard, in which the period of production of agricultural products associated with natural biological factors and the period of product sales in the market play an important role.
	- in order to modernize the agrarian sphere with a new technological procedure, it is necessary to create conditions worthy of Agriculture, justify the rules that promote access to a competitive market, identify skills that allow employees to effectively use the capabilities of the digital economy, and identify scientific institutions responsible for achieving the maximum effect.

According to Ayupov, the main goals of the Digital Economy program are highlighted ^[5].

It is proposed to consider the main tasks of the digital transformation mechanism within three groups: preparation for digital transformation, its planning and regulation.

Preparation for updating digital transformation processes within the framework of the first group: assessment of the level of technical and technological development of the subject; assessment of institutional conditions; assessment of the quality of Information Infrastructure; assessment of the level of integration into a single information space; assessment of institutional conditions; assessment of financial capabilities.

Planning digital transform processes within the second group: substantiating the priorities of digital transform; substantiating the strategy and model of digital development; choosing digital technologies and tools for their implementation; assessing the effectiveness of alternative digital transform options; developing a promising plan for digital transform; identifying the need for financial resources.

Regulation of digital transform processes within the framework of the third group: optimization of interaction within the framework of the digital ecosystem; implementation of the functions of the current digital platform; ensuring a sufficient level of Internet technologies – training of personnel; adjusting the speed of digital transform processes; adjusting the scale of digital transform, digitizing individual elements.

Semyachkov said that it is important to consider the main aspects of the development of the digital economy and make decisions about its role in the overall system of economic relations ^[6].

¹ Source: Developed by the author on the basis of scientific research.

The scope of digital transformation processes prioritizes the tasks of developing a strategy for digitizing Agro-economic systems of various levels, which includes not only the choice of priorities for the introduction of digital technologies, but also the means of their implementation.

The basis for determining the effectiveness of individual measures for digitizing the agricultural production system is based on the results of calculations provided by the developers of digital technologies, aimed at aggressively advancing a digital product, or expert assessments that only allow assessing the potential effectiveness of specific measures.

As a result, the productivity of agriculture, including the use of resources of agricultural sectors, is expanding.

Digital assets of industrial enterprises allow you to instantly respond to new market challenges and further develop both existing technologies and model innovative products ^[7].

Today, the acceleration of informatization is the basis for ensuring the stability of future development. Consistent economic growth is based on innovation and investment.

The direction of the development of the innovation process is digital technologies in crop production and animal husbandry, the introduction of scientific achievements in production ^[8].

Digital agricultural crops that make it possible to increase agricultural efficiency. The mode of operation of modern information technologies includes agricultural crops, crop planning, automation of irrigation, and the procedure for operation, from digital modeling of crops to calculating feed for raising cattle.

Due to the production and introduction of modern information technologies in agriculture, not only productivity increases, but also financial and labor-related costs decrease. As a result, the quality of the product increases and the profit increases.

According to the socio-economic status of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2019, the gross domestic product amounted to 25.4 billion dollar was in the production of goods. the in 2020. \$ 31.1 billion increased to dollars. At the same time, in 2019, 17.0 billion in the services sector. dollar, and in 2020. 19.6 billion there was a dollar increase. Net taxes on products in 2019 amounted to Rs 4.1 billion. dollar, in 2020. amounted to \$4.8 billion.

As of the end of 2021, GDP is 38.1 billion in the production of goods. \$ 23.9 billion in the field of services. gross value added in the amount of dollars was created, net taxes on products amounted to \$4.8 billion (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Gross domestic product by socio-economic status in 2019-2021

The transition to a digital economy is today one of the main priorities for the development of the country's agricultural sector, since the exact level of digitization demonstrates the competitiveness of the country in the new technological order. Therefore, in order to reach a new stage of economic development of Uzbekistan, social networks need their own scientific solutions and advanced development.

2 Source: Developed by the author on the basis of scientific research.

The formation of data centers and modern internet technology platforms designed for systematization and analytical processing of information is the basis of new economic technologies. In this case, it is important to develop a direction that provides services related to management consulting and business analysis.

The driving forces also include technologies that can provide a fast and reliable connection. Currently, the global trend is the introduction and development of 5G technology [9].

As a consequence of production, processing, research and other things, they extract a positive effect from the result of the exchange ratio – a benefit. In the digital economy, information and data act as objects of consumption [10].

The importance of the digital economy network–digital technologies dramatically change more than 60-80% of the sectors associated with the economy of the agricultural sector. This view is based on the fact that information technology and digital platforms dramatically change business models, eliminating intermediaries in optimizing their efficiency and processes.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the digital economy is a dynamically developing form of economic activity of the information society. It penetrates into all sectors of Agriculture and occupies a reliable place in the real sector of the economy. The digital economy is rapidly changing the usual forms and methods of economic life around the world.

There is uncertainty in the development of Agriculture. On the one hand, there are positive results: in a number of areas, the volume of production has increased, the number of enterprises with profitable activities is increasing. But on the other hand, negative processes that outweigh positive shifts remain and continue to develop, which makes it possible to assess the situation in an area that does not respond to economic development tasks in general as difficult.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 4

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

